

INSTRUCTIONAL ATTRIBUTES AND TLE TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE: A BASIS FOR COMPETENCY-BASED TRAINING PROGRAM

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Instructional Attributes and TLE Teachers' Performance: A Basis For Competency-Based Training Program

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Abstract

The study assessed the instructional attributes and TLE teachers' performance by prescribed TESDA and DepEd regulations. It determined the teachers' profile and instructional attributes along the four areas of TLE. It also measured the performance of TLE teachers in content knowledge, pedagogical approach, classroom management, ICT integration, and assessment and evaluation. The descriptive-correlational design was used, with a researcher-made questionnaire as the main data-gathering instrument. Results revealed that the majority of the respondents are 26 years old and the majority are female. Additionally, majority of the respondents are single and are specialized in Home Economics. Moreover, majority of the respondents have been teaching for less than 10 years and attained a bachelor's degree. Based on the result of the study, it revealed that TLE teachers are competent with their instructional attributes in terms of Home Economics, Industrial Arts, ICT, and Agri-Fishery Arts, as with their performance. The profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, and highest educational attainment, is not statistically significant with their instructional attributes. Moreover, it showed a significant difference for Home Economics, Industrial Arts, and Agri-Fishery Arts, while ICT is not significant when grouped according to area of specialization. It also revealed that the profile of the respondents does not moderate relationship with TLE teachers' instructional attributes and performance. This became the basis for the output which is a competency-based training program.

Keywords: *competency-based training program, instructional attributes, Technology And Livelihood Education, teachers' performance, technology*

Introduction

Competency is a fundamental need for hiring and advancement in every professional sector. It entails the professional expertise, effort, and understanding that are all necessary to complete the task at hand (Nijveldt, et al., 2001). According to Main and Hammond (2008), competency also includes human qualities that, when possessed and used, result in the accomplishment of a job or position. Competencies in education build upon one another; as learning improves, fundamental competencies are moved on to advanced levels (Council on Education for Public Health, 2006).

A teacher's competency in the professional realm of teaching includes social, professional, and personal components. This includes controlling learning processes, adapting to one's environment, and teaching as an expert in the subject and ideas pertaining to teaching and learning (Klassen & Chiu, 2010). Many teacher education institutions across the world look at how to use competencies to support teachers' professional growth without sacrificing the caliber of instruction. Teachers typically enroll in pre-service education programs, but this does not ensure that they will be competent to satisfy the expectations of development. Thus, in order to improve teachers' effectiveness and competence, schools must constantly assess and support their initial and continuing professional development.

Teachers are essential in molding and readying the next generation of citizens to compete in the twenty-first century. They are regarded as the most crucial educational system resources. They give an organization its own character, make it function, and give it life. The caliber and skill of an educational institution's faculty greatly influences its overall quality. Therefore, it is imperative to guarantee that teachers are competent, particularly in subjects like technology and livelihood education that directly affect society.

One of the topics in the Department of Education's (DepEd) Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum is Technology and Livelihood Education. Students who take this course will learn competencies that are highly applicable to daily life. The Department of Education has established a Technical Vocational section inside the Bureau of Secondary Education to emphasize its value in the K-12 Basic Education Program (BEP). As one of the three main strands that will equip high school graduates with employable skills, they believe that this section has to be strengthened.

The K-12 Basic Education Program's technical and vocational education courses primarily aim to equip students with the theoretical and practical skills they need to succeed in the workforce. It is anticipated that the students possess the requisite expertise in their respective fields to effectively navigate the demands of the job market.

Considering the aforementioned, one of the main objectives of the K-12 curriculum is to prepare students for the workforce. The Technical Education and Skills Development Authority, or TESDA, sets the guidelines for the junior high school (JHS) TLE, or Technologies and Livelihood Education, courses. This will allow the students to earn a national certification (NC) required by the industry, which students can eventually get once they enter senior high school

In Grades 7 and 8, every TLE topic is exploratory in nature. This implies that every student has the opportunity to investigate the four primary TLE courses: Industrial Arts, Home Economics, Information and Communications Technology (ICT), and Agri-Fishery Arts.

Pupils may select up to four TLE minicourses in Grade 7 and an additional four in Grade 8, depending on what the school offers and the needs of the surrounding community and facilities. The student does not yet receive a Certificate of Competency (COC) in Grades 7 and 8. The exploratory courses serve as a prerequisite for obtaining an NC I/II in grade 10 and a COC in grade 9, courses are a prelude to earning a COC in Grade 9 and an NC I/II in 10th grade.

From the experimental courses selected in the seventh and eighth grades, the student selects one course to concentrate on in the ninth grade. The student is eligible to receive a COC at this level. The student continues with the TLE specialization course they choose in ninth grade in grade 10. This enables the student, depending on the TLE course selected, to receive at least an NC Level I or II (NC I or II).

Students enrolled in Grade 11 will take a necessary specialized course in addition to their core studies. The three primary tracks are Sports and Arts, Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL), and Academic. Students will continue the TLE course they took in grades nine and ten if they choose the TVL track as their senior high school specialty.

By doing this, students will be able to obtain NC II, which they can use as proof of eligibility when they apply for jobs following their graduation from SHS. However, if the students choose to continue their education, they can follow the TVL track and graduate with a bachelor's degree in a related profession.

Despite this well-thought-out program, there have been many difficulties in the global academic arena, particularly in TVET institutions. As a result, TVET teachers of all ages must update their competencies and engage in continuous learning (Ali, 2015). Thus, emerging nations must qualified educators by putting in place efficient systems of instruction, training, and preparation. To remain competitive, educational institutions must provide qualified educators with cutting-edge knowledge and abilities to tackle the demands of modern education and the workplace (Salleh, Sulaiman & Frederiksen, 2014). The seeming disconnects between what is taught in schools and what is required in the workplace is one of these difficulties.

Throughout the teaching-learning process, it is imperative that the teacher possesses all of the performance skills recommended by the pedagogical approach. This will enable them to better support students' learning, foster collaborative learning, squelch boredom, and enable individualized instruction.

Deepali Shah (2023) asserts that excellent pedagogical abilities are essential for instructors, including content understanding both inside and outside of the curriculum, classroom management techniques, ICT integration, assessment, and evaluation. These skills are so important that they have the potential to have a big impact on students' academic success. Furthermore, when teachers do exceptionally well, they are able to evaluate their strategies and tactics for teaching and learning and help students become experts in even the most difficult subjects or themes.

Research Questions

This study assessed the instructional attributes of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in Maryhill College, Inc., Lucena City relative to their performance by the prescribed TESDA regulations. Specifically, it aimed to accomplish the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. area of specialization;
 - 1.5. number of years in teaching; and
 - 1.6. highest educational attainment?
2. How do the respondents perceive their instructional attributes along the four areas of TLE, namely:
 - 2.1. Home Economics;
 - 2.2. Industrial Arts;
 - 2.3. Information and Communication Technology; and
 - 2.4. Agri-Fishery Arts?
3. What is the level of performance of TLE teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. knowledge of content within and across the curriculum teaching areas;
 - 3.2. pedagogical approach;
 - 3.3. classroom management;
 - 3.4. integration of ICT; and
 - 3.5. assessment and evaluation?
4. Is there a significant relationship between TLE teacher's instructional attributes and their performance?
5. Do the perceived instructional attributes of the respondents significantly differ when the respondents are grouped according to age, sex, civil status, and area of specialization?
6. Does the profile of the respondents moderate the relationship between TLE teachers' instructional attributes and performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive-correlational method of research as it aims to determine the instructional attributes and performance of TLE teachers in Maryhill College and its relationship. Descriptive correlational research is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. This research design was selected as it can be used to assess the characteristics of individuals or groups of physical environments such as teachers of particular schools. The study used this method in gathering data and information towards the development of a competency- based training program for TLE, geared of enhancing the performance of TLE teachers.

Respondents

The researcher utilized purposive sampling. The respondents of the study were twenty (20) TLE teachers from Maryhill College and must meet the following criteria: (1) TLE teacher from Maryhill College with at least 1 year in service, (2) must be teaching TLE subject of any components/areas, (3) and willing to be part of this research undertaking.

Instrument

The study utilized a self-made questionnaire, as the main gathering tool. The survey questionnaire was developed in fidelity to the specific objectives stated as reasons for constructing the study. It was based on the concepts and related studies as inputs to the instrument. The instrument was used to answer the research objectives related to the instructional attributes of TLE teachers and their performance.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part focused on the profile of TLE teachers, including age, sex, civil status, area of specialization, number of years in teaching, and highest educational attainment. The second part included the instructional attributes of TLE teachers in the four areas: Home Economics, Agri-Fishery Arts, Information and Communications Technology, and Industrial Arts. The last part involved the performance of TLE teachers in terms of knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas, pedagogical approach, classroom management, integration of ICT, assessment and evaluation. Experts in the field of research were requested to evaluate, in independent rounds, if the questionnaire has theory, construction, or content validity. The results of the validation were incorporated into the final design of the instrument. Also, a reliability test was conducted to ensure the reliability of the instrument. Cronbach's alpha was used for this purpose.

Procedure

The researcher used the descriptive-survey method of research where the quantitative data was collected through questionnaire from respondents' responses. The questionnaire after its validation was used as a tool in gathering the data. The researcher made a letter signed by the research adviser and approved by the School Administrators. Before any data-gathering activity, an initial permit from the school President was solicited.

Afterward, the researcher asked the permission from the principal of the target school. Upon securing the necessary permission, the researcher started to distribute the questionnaire to the respondents. The respondents were asked to answer the questionnaire after permission was granted. The responses were kept confidential; Data Privacy Act is also strictly being followed in the use of information given by the respondents. The respondents were guided in cases where they needed additional explanations related to the items given in the questionnaire. A week was given to the respondents for them to analyze the items carefully. Follow-ups was made as necessary, while still ensuring that no pressure was given to the respondents. After the allotted time, the questionnaire was retrieved by the researcher and the gathered data was be tabulated, analyzed and statistically interpreted.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion of the assessment on the instructional attributes of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in Maryhill College, Inc., Lucena City relative to their performance following the prescribed TESDA regulations. The findings were supported by statistical data as found on their accompanying tabular forms with their corresponding interpretation and analysis, duly supported and justified by the review of related literature and studies.

Part 1. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
26 Years Old	12	60.0
27 Years Old	2	10.0
29 Years Old	2	10.0
32 Years Old	2	10.0
38 Years Old	2	10.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 2. *Distribution of the Respondents in terms of Sex*

	Frequency	Percent
Male	6	30.0
Female	14	70.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 3. *Frequency Distribution of the Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status*

	Frequency	Percent
Single	16	80.0
Married	4	20.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 4. *Frequency Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Area of Specialization*

Specialization	Frequency	Percent
Home Economics	9	45.0
Industrial Arts	4	20.0
Information & Communication Technology	5	25.0
Agri-Fishery Arts	2	10.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 5. *Frequency Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Number of Years Teaching*

Number of Years Teaching	Frequency	Percent
Less Than 10 Years	18	90.0
10 - 19 Years	2	10.0
Total	20	100.0

Table 6. *Frequency Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Attainment*

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	17	85.0
Master's Degree	3	15.0
Total	20	100.0

Part 2. Instructional Attributes of TLE Teachers along the Four Areas of TLE

Table 7. *Perceived Instructional Attributes of TLE Teachers Along the Area of Home Economics*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Improve attitudes toward Home Economics	3.10	0.79	MC
2. Promote transfer of learning from the classroom to the home	2.85	0.75	MC
3. Create more interest in and understanding of concepts of homemaking	2.85	0.81	MC
4. Be responsible citizens and informed consumers willing to contribute to the well-being of individuals, families, and society in terms of meeting basic human needs	3.00	0.73	MC
5. Demonstrate good use of management and organizational skills in handling physical and socio-economic resources for self, family, community, and society	2.80	0.52	MC
6. Develop capability, values, and attitudes to make informed decisions that foster a healthy lifestyle and contribute positively to the social and economic future of a society	3.15	0.75	MC
7. Analyze contextual factors contributing to the well-being of individuals, families, and society with an application of knowledge from the Home Economics	3.20	0.52	MC
8. Implement strategies to solve complicated problems in technological contexts in particular, food/fashion, using a range of appropriate techniques and procedures	3.10	0.72	MC
9. Evaluate critically the impact of social, cultural, economic, scientific, and technological developments on the well-being of individuals, families, and society as a whole	3.20	0.77	MC
10. Develop an aesthetic sense and creativity through the design and production processes	3.00	0.56	MC
Overall	3.03	0.47	MC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 8. *Perceived Instructional Attributes of TLE Teachers Along the Area Industrial Arts*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Observe safety precautions in doing tasks or work	3.10	0.72	MC
2. Read and follow instructions before using equipment	3.10	0.79	MC
3. Observe occupational health and safety practices	3.15	0.59	MC

4. Be able to work effectively with team members and maintain effective relationship	3.15	0.67	MC
5. Perform mensuration and calculations in jobs-related problems	2.90	0.72	MC
6. Supervise proper use and maintenance of tools and equipment	3.20	0.62	MC
7. Observe the economy in the use of supplies and materials	3.05	0.76	MC
8. Ensure compliance with standard procedures, specifications, and manuals of instructions	3.00	0.73	MC
9. Demonstrate proper handling and maintenance of electrical measuring instruments	2.80	0.79	MC
10. Use the required working uniform, mash, and goggles in the shop room	2.85	0.67	MC
Overall	3.06	0.50	MC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 9. Perceived Instructional Attributes of TLE Teachers Along the Area ICT

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Use computers and other technologies to collect and communicate information to students, colleagues, parents, and others	3.80	0.41	VC
2. Use appropriate office and teaching productivity tools	3.40	0.68	VC
3. Reflects on the use of ICT in their profession for development and innovation	3.35	0.67	VC
4. Demonstrate knowledge and skills in basic computer operation and other information devices, including basic troubleshooting and maintenance.	3.45	0.51	VC
5. Make use of networks to access information, colleagues, and outside sources	3.10	0.64	MC
6. Understand and effectively use the internet and network applications and resources	3.70	0.47	VC
7. Apply technology to develop students' higher-order thinking skills and creativity	3.55	0.51	VC
8. Provide performance tasks that require students to locate and analyze information and use a variety of media to clearly communicate results	3.40	0.68	VC
9. Apply technology to facilitate a variety of appropriate assessment and evaluation strategies recognizing the diversity of learners	3.55	0.51	VC
10. Evaluate usage of ICT integration in the teaching-learning process and use the results to refine the design of learning activities	3.25	0.55	MC
Overall	3.46	0.30	VC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 10. Perceived Instructional Attributes of TLE Teachers Along the Area Agri-fishery

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Clean the work area according to the 5S principle	3.15	0.75	MC
2. Determine areas of concern for safety measures	2.95	0.83	MC
3. Apply appropriate safety measures	3.05	0.51	MC
4. Wear appropriate PPE as prescribed by OSHA	2.90	0.64	MC
5. Apply principles of the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) accordingly	2.95	0.60	MC
6. Perform preventive maintenance of tools and equipment through routine check-up and maintenance	3.15	0.59	MC
7. Perform basic workplace calculation and estimation	3.00	0.73	MC
8. Select and operate farm tools and equipment	3.20	0.52	MC
9. Safe keep tools, materials, and outfits as determined by safety protocols	2.95	0.69	MC
10. Perform monitoring of pest incidence based on the prescribed procedure	2.75	0.64	MC
Overall	3.01	0.46	MC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Part 3. Level of Performance of TLE Teachers

Table 11. Level of Performance of TLE Teachers in terms of Knowledge of Content within and across Curriculum Teaching Areas

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Motivate learners to create and establish connections between subject matters	3.45	0.51	VC
2. Use examples from other teaching areas to make explanations concrete and forceful	3.40	0.50	VC
3. Encourage students to investigate the content area to expand their knowledge and satisfy their natural curiosity	3.40	0.60	C
4. Demonstrate a knowledge of their subject by relating it to other disciplines	3.55	0.60	VC
5. Demonstrate an appropriate level of content knowledge in their specialty	3.50	0.51	VC
6. Understand students' cultural backgrounds, interests, skills, and abilities as they apply across a range of learning domains and/or subject areas	3.40	0.50	VC
7. Understand the influence of diversity and planning instruction accordingly	3.25	0.91	MC
8. Relate subject matter to contents from other learning areas	3.25	0.55	MC
9. Understand students' motivations and their interests in specific class content	3.45	0.51	VC
10. Use materials or lessons that counteract stereotypes and acknowledge the contributions of all culture	3.20	0.70	MC
Overall	3.39	0.31	VC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 12. *Level of Performance of TLE Teachers in terms of Pedagogical Approach*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Encourage students to articulate thoughts and ideas clearly and effectively	3.60	0.60	VC
2. Help engage students in active learning opportunities	3.60	0.50	VC
3. Integrate specific instruction that helps students develop the ability to apply processes and strategies for critical thinking and problem-solving	3.75	0.44	VC
4. Use a variety of methods and materials suited to the needs of all students	3.35	0.75	VC
5. Promote the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and performance capabilities	3.55	0.60	VC
6. Help students assume responsibility for identifying and using learning resources	3.61	0.26	VC
7. Identify gains and difficulties students are experiencing in learning and performing	3.60	0.68	VC
8. Use a variety of methods to communicate effectively with all students and a variety of research-verified approaches to improve teaching and learning	3.50	0.51	VC
9. Give contingent, specific, and credible praise and feedback	3.75	0.44	VC
10. Reflect on the impact of strategies used in teaching based on actual results	3.35	0.75	VC
Overall	3.57	0.32	VC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 13. *Level of Performance of TLE Teachers in Terms of Classroom Management*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Maintain a safe and orderly classroom that facilitates student learning	3.50	0.69	VC
2. Manage student behavior positively through effective communication to defuse and deescalate disruptive or dangerous behavior	3.30	0.47	VC
3. Maintain a positive and nurturing learning environment	3.20	0.70	MC
4. Promote teamwork, planning, and communication	3.40	0.50	VC
5. Implement policies and practices positively affecting students' learning	3.55	0.51	VC
6. Promote positive relationships, cooperation, and purposeful learning	3.40	0.50	VC
7. Maximize efficiency through maintained discipline and morale	3.30	0.57	VC
8. Use positive methods of discipline and set age-appropriate rules	3.65	0.49	VC
9. Ensure the active and equitable engagement of students in productive tasks through organizing, assigning, and managing, time, space, and activities	3.40	0.50	VC
10. Structure the classroom accordingly to maintain order and cleanliness	3.40	0.50	VC
Overall	3.41	0.35	VC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 14. *Level of Performance of TLE Teachers as to Integration of Information and Communications Technology*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Integrate technology into instruction to maximize student learning	3.50	0.51	VC
2. Apply technology to facilitate a variety of appropriate assessment and evaluation strategies recognizing the diversity of learners	3.65	0.49	VC
3. Know when and how to use current educational technology, as well as the most appropriate type and level of technology	3.40	0.50	VC
4. Utilize ICT as a means for efficient and effective teaching and learning situation	3.35	0.49	VC
5. Demonstrate knowledge and skills in information and data management	3.20	0.41	MC
6. Use computers and other technologies to collect and communicate information to students, colleagues, parents, and others	3.55	0.51	VC
7. Show real materials or tools and equipment to understand the key concepts or skills	3.50	0.51	VC
8. Consider the learning resource management and development system portal as a source of teaching materials	3.50	0.51	VC
9. Understand and effectively use the internet and network applications and resources	3.45	0.51	VC
10. Know the most appropriate type and level of technology	3.35	0.49	VC
Overall	3.45	0.25	VC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Table 15. *Level of Performance of TLE Teachers in terms of Assessment and Evaluation*

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1. Monitoring student progress toward instructional goals	2.95	0.60	MC
2. Report assessment results for school-level analysis, evaluation, and decision-making	3.65	0.67	VC
3. Evaluate student progress using a variety of assessment-data measuring goals and draw on appropriate data to develop classroom and instructional plans	3.35	0.49	VC
4. Collaborate with colleagues to monitor student performance and make instruction responsive to cultural differences and individual learning needs	3.20	0.62	MC
5. Communicate strengths and weaknesses based on assessment results to students, and parents or guardians	3.35	0.49	VC
6. Use multiple indicators, both formative and summative, to monitor and evaluate student progress, provide evidence that students are attaining 21st-century knowledge, skills, and dispositions	3.55	0.69	VC
7. Use data to provide ideas about what can be done to improve student learning	3.05	0.22	MC

8.	Analyze assessment information gathered before and during instruction to understand each student's progress to date and to inform future instructional planning	2.60	0.50	MC
9.	Display an ability to use appropriate data to identify areas of need that should be addressed in a school improvement plan	2.95	0.76	MC
10.	Identify developmental levels of individual students and plan instruction accordingly, assess and use resources needed to address the strengths and weaknesses of students	2.75	0.44	MC
Overall		3.14	0.32	MC

Legend: 3.50-4.00 Very Competent (VC); 2.50-3.49 Moderately Competent (MC); 1.50-2.49 Slightly Competent (SC); 1.00-1.49 Least Competent (LC)

Part 4. Significant Relationship between TLE Teacher's Instructional Attributes and Performance.

Table 16. Result of the Significant Relationship between TLE Teachers' Instructional Attributes and their Performance

	A	B	C	D	E
Home Economics	0.284	0.173	0.002	0.128	-0.054
Industrial Arts	-0.384	-0.139	0.045	0.044	0.253
Information & Communication Technology	-0.048	-0.012	0.275	0.215	0.127
Agri-Fishery Arts	-0.146	-0.087	-0.068	0.199	0.042

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)
 * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
 Legend: A – Knowledge of Content within and across Curriculum Teaching Areas
 B – Pedagogical Approach
 C – Classroom Management
 D – Integration of ICT
 E – Assessment and Evaluation

Part 5. Significant Difference between Instructional Attributes when grouped according to Profile

Table 17. Significant Difference between Instructional Attributes and Respondent's Age

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Home Economics	0.446	4	0.111	0.455	0.767
	3.672	15	0.245		
	4.118	19			
Industrial Arts	1.034	4	0.258	1.067	0.407
	3.634	15	0.242		
	4.668	19			
Information & Communication Technology	0.380	4	0.095	1.089	0.397
	1.309	15	0.087		
	1.690	19			
Agri-Fishery Arts	1.238	4	0.309	1.628	0.219
	2.852	15	0.190		
	4.090	19			

Table 18. Significant Difference between Instructional Attributes and Respondents' Sex

	SD	T	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean
Home Economics	Male	2.87	0.46	0.996	18
	Female	3.09	0.47		
Industrial Arts	Male	3.15	0.47	0.521	18
	Female	3.02	0.52		
Information Communication Technology	Male	3.42	0.31	0.368	18
	Female	3.47	0.30		
Agri-Fishery Arts	Male	3.12	0.49	0.695	18
	Female	2.96	0.46		

Table 19. Significant Difference between Instructional Attributes and Respondent's Civil Status

	Mean	SD	T	Df	Sig.(2-tailed)
Home Economics	Single	3.02	0.47	-0.117	18
	Married	3.05	0.53		
Industrial Arts	Single	3.11	0.49	0.828	18
	Married	2.88	0.53		
Information & Communication Technology	Single	3.47	0.25	0.403	18
	Married	3.40	0.50		
Agri- Fisheries and Arts	Single	3.11	0.46	2.125	18
	Married	2.60	0.22		

Table 19 shows the results on the significant difference between instructional attributes and respondent's civil status. A T-test was used to determine its result. This revealed that there is no difference on the instructional attributes and respondent's civil status. Specifically,

Home Economics is not statistically significant to civil status with ($p=.908$), Industrial Arts is not statistically significant to civil status with ($p=.419$), Information and Communication and Technology is not statistically significant to civil status with ($p=.692$), and Agri-fishery is also not statistically significant to civil status with ($p=.408$). This revealed that the civil status of TLE teachers has nothing to do with their instructional attributes. Moreover, revealed that no difference in the level of competency of teachers in the four areas of TLE. This indicates that marital status may not influence their ability to teach the TLE subject. This may also be attributed to the fact that elementary teachers as generalists are expected to deliver only basic knowledge and skills to the pupils. The result of this study is in agreement with the study conducted by Oselumese, et al. (2016) which showed that marital status did not significantly influence the effectiveness of teacher.

Table 20. Significant Difference between Instructional Attributes and Respondents Years of Teaching

		Mean	SD	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Home Economics	Less than 10 years	3.02	0.44	0.078	18	0.939
	10 - 19 years	3.05	0.92			
Industrial Arts	Less than 10 years	3.07	0.48	0.176	18	0.862
	0 - 19 years	3.00	0.85			
Information & Communication Technology	Less than 10 years	3.42	0.29	1.828	18	0.084
	10 - 19 years	3.80	0.14			
Agri-Fisheries Arts	Less than 10 years	3.07	0.45	5.286	14	0.090
	10 - 19 years	2.45	0.07			

Table 21. Significant Difference between Instructional Attributes and Respondents According to Area of Specialization

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Home Economics	Between Groups	2.822	3	0.941	11.618	0.000
	Within Groups	1.296	16	0.081		
	Total	4.118	19			
Industrial Arts	Between Groups	3.439	3	1.146	14.917	0.000
	Within Groups	1.229	16	0.077		
	Total	4.668	19			
Information & Communication Technology	Between Groups	0.232	3	0.077	0.851	0.486
	Within Groups	1.457	16	0.091		
	Total	1.690	19			
Agri-Fisheries Arts	Between Groups	1.804	3	0.601	4.208	0.023
	Within Groups	2.286	16	0.143		
	Total	4.090	19			

Part 6. Moderation Effect of Profile of the Respondents to their Attributes and Performance

Table 22. Results on the Respondent's Profile and TLE Teacher's Instructional Attributes and Performance

Moderators	p-value	Interpretation
Sex	.730	not significant
civil status	.663	not significant
area of specialization	.538	not significant
years of service	.278	not significant
highest educational attainment	.558	not significant

On the demographic profile of the respondents, result showed that from the total of 20 respondents, 60% or 12 respondents are 26 years old, and the other percentage was distributed to 27, 29, 32, and 38 years old. In terms of sex, the majority of the respondents are female with a percentage of 70% or exactly 14 respondents, and 30% or 6 respondents are male. Moreover, most of the respondents are single with the percentage of 80% or exactly 16 respondents, while 20% or 4 respondents are married. In terms of area of specialization, the majority of the respondents are Home Economics major with a frequency of 9 and an equivalent percentage of 45%, 5 respondents have a major of Information and Communications Technology or 25%, 20% or exactly 4 are Industrial Arts, and there are 2 respondents or 10% of the entire population with the major of Agriculture. Based on the findings, the result showed that majority of the respondents have been teaching for less than 10 years with a frequency of 18 or 90% of the entire population. 2 or 10% of the respondents are teaching for 10-19 years. Lastly, in terms of highest educational attainment, the majority of the respondents, or 85% or exactly 17 respondents are bachelor's degrees, while 15% or 3 respondents are master's degrees.

On the perceived instructional attributes of TLE teachers along the area of Home Economics, it shows that the respondents are moderately competent which is supported by ($WM=3.03$, $SD=.47$). Specifically, respondents rated "Analyze contextual factors contributing to the well-being of individual, family, and society with the application of knowledge from the Home Economics and Evaluate critically the impact of social, cultural, economic, scientific and technological developments on the well-being of individuals, families, and society as a whole" the highest with ($WM=3.20$). In Industrial Arts, findings shows that the respondents are moderately

competent on the perceived instructional attributes of TLE teachers which is supported by (WM=3.06, SD=.50). Specifically, respondents rated “Supervise proper use and maintenance of tools and equipment” rated the most with (WM=3.20, SD=.62). Moreover, respondents are very competent on the perceived instructional attributes of TLE teachers in ICT which is supported by (WM=3.46, SD=.30) specifically, “Use computers and other technologies to collect and communicate information to students, colleagues, parents, and others” rated the most with (WM=3.80, SD=.41) and “Make use of networks to access information, colleagues, and outside sources” rated the least with (WM=3.10, SD=.64). Based on the findings, it shows that the respondents are moderately competent on the perceived instructional attributes of TLE teachers in Agri-fishery which is supported by (WM=3.01, SD=.46). Particularly, “Select and operate farm tools and equipment” rated the most with (WM=3.20, SD=.52).

On the Level of Performance of TLE Teachers in terms of Knowledge of Content, result shows that the TLE teachers have a very competent level of performance which is supported by (WM=3.39, SD=.31). Particularly, respondents rated “Demonstrate a knowledge of their subject by relating it to other disciplines” the most with (WM=3.55, SD=.60). Based on the findings, result shows that the TLE teachers have a very competent level of performance in terms of Pedagogical Approach which is supported by (WM=3.57, SD=.32). Particularly, respondents rated “Integrate specific instruction that helps students develop the ability to apply processes and strategies for critical thinking and problem solving” and “Give contingent, specific, and credible praise and feedback” rated the highest with (WM=3.75, SD=.44). In terms of classroom management, result shows that the TLE teachers have a very competent level of performance which is supported by (WM=3.41, SD=.35). Particularly, respondents rated “Use positive methods of discipline and set rules that are age appropriate” with (WM=3.65, SD=.49). In terms of Integration of ICT, result shows that the TLE teachers have a very competent level of performance which is supported by (WM=3.45, SD=.25). Specifically, statements “Apply technology to facilitate a variety of appropriate assessment and evaluation strategies recognizing the diversity of learners” rated the most with (WM=3.69, SD=.49). Finally, result shows teachers have a very competent level of performance in terms of assessment and evaluation which is supported by (WM=3.14, SD=.32). Specifically, statements “Report assessment results for school-level analysis, evaluation, and decision-making” rated the most with (WM=3.65, SD=.67).

On the significant relationship between TLE Teacher's Instructional Attributes and their Performance. Based on the findings, show that there is no significant relationship between TLE teacher's instructional attributes and their performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

On the significant difference between instructional attributes and respondent's profile. Based on the findings, results revealed that age is not statistically significant to instructional attributes. Also, sex showed that it is not statistically significant to instructional attributes. Meanwhile, civil status is not statistically significant to instructional attributes. Also, instructional attributes are not significant to age. Moreover, it showed a significant difference for home economics, Industrial arts, and Agri-Fishery Arts, while ICT shows a not significant result when grouped into areas of specialization.

On respondents' profiles and its relationship to TLE teachers' instructional attributes and performance, results revealed that the profile does not moderate the instructional attributes and performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher provides the following conclusions:

The result revealed that there is no significant relationship among TLE teachers' instructional attributes and their performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

On the significant difference between instructional attributes and respondent's profile. Results revealed that age, sex, civil status, number of years in teaching, and highest educational attainment is not statistically significant to instructional attributes. Moreover, it showed a significant difference for Home Economics, Industrial Arts, and Agri-Fishery Arts, while ICT showed a not significant result when grouped into areas of specialization.

The profile of the respondents does not moderate the relationship between the instructional attributes and performance of TLE teachers. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The TLE Teachers and school administrators may have a goal-oriented action in attaining proficiency through integrative and collaborative activities as part of the competency-based training program.

The TLE teachers and the school administrators may inclusively create equal opportunities for everyone to tap their knowledge bases and resources.

The proposed competency-based training program may be tried out to test the usefulness of its implementation.

Similar researches in other learning areas may be done to further validate and strengthen the findings of this study.

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